
EFFECTIVE USE OF INTERNET AND WEB TECHNOLOGY IN ACADEMIC COLLEGE LIBRARIES: A STUDY

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Abstract:

The internet and Web Technology is most important role in a digital revolution for academic college libraries. The research study is intended to study the effective use of internet and web technology in academic college libraries in Mangalwedha City. This study also depend on of academic college Libraries. This study reduced on use of library however effective use of internet and web technology. This paper attempts discuss the fast development of internet and Web Technology in the development of library services is an active reaction to challenges for academic college libraries. The effective use of internet and web technology especially by the college students by using the some freely available tools over the internet. The study for impact of Internet and Web technology fully use and effectiveness of academic college Libraries in Mangalwedha city colleges affiliated by Solapur University, Solapur.

Keywords: Academic College Libraries, Internet, Web Technology, Web Based Resources, Open Sources.

Introduction:

Academic College Library is a central responsibility for better functioning of an educational institution. Academic libraries have an important role to play in providing equal access to information. If the purpose of education is learning, then the library is an indispensable source of learning. The Web Technology is no substitute for library as only a small percentage of information contained in print is on the Internet. Academic College libraries are facing more challenges as they enter the digital era. Increasing amounts of the material they acquire is being produced in digital formats, and college and university students are especially sophisticated users of the new

information technology and are increasingly insistent that coursework and course readings be accessible via the Internet and Web Technology.

The Effective use of Internet and Web technology in Academic College Libraries. This study including web based technology an effective use in library. The revolution on web based and web enabled products and services conceptualized by Academic College Libraries in Mangalwedha City. This has been a great challenge and opportunity for in delivery of various products to the end-user in all academic college libraries. It has given great opportunity for Library and Information Science professionals to provide new services for users. Web based

technology has increased information for users. Even the government services and e-governance has been making use of web media including developing libraries. It accelerates with higher rate in coming year as the internet usage data is on galloping height. Higher education sector is being the prime segment in shaping the human resource potentials by adopting newer technologies.

Use Of Internet And Web Technology:

Many people are using internet and web technology to find information, friends, chatting or for their interest of area. The question is how effectively they are using internet especially concerned with new users and college students. Let us take an example, suppose a user need to login to Facebook, and click on the first link of the result page. For this we have to cross the three to four steps, instead of doing this every time we can directly use the address bar by typing the www.facebook.com or by doing bookmarking directly we can enter the home page of the any website. For the effective use of internet and web technology firstly user should develop some search strategies according to their need of the information. Then go for the search or browse of internet and other technology.

There are following Open access system are available in Academic College libraries.

DOAJ: (Directory Of Open Access Journals):

The aim of the DOAJ is to increase the visibility and ease of use of open access scientific and scholarly journals, thereby promoting their increased usage and impact. The DOAJ aims to be comprehensive and cover all open access

scientific and scholarly journals that use a quality control system to guarantee the content. In short, the DOAJ aims to be the one-stop shop for users of open access journals. The content of DOAJ is available freely through <http://www.doaj.org/> website without any embargo period. Almost all scholarly and scientific subjects humanity, science, social science, management, law, etc., periodical are covered that publish research review papers in full text. It will accept all academic, government, commercial, non-profit private sources. It consists of 9804 journals, 5636 Journals searchable at Article level and 1573847 Articles.

Meta Search Engines:

Meta search engine is a search engine which search simultaneously more than one search engine indexes to retrieve the required information for a user. Meta search engines display their results in two ways Single List- Most of Meta search engines exhibit multiple-engine search outcomes in a single combined list, from which replica records have been detached. Multiple Lists- Some of the Meta search engines do not organize multiple-engine search fallouts but present them instead in distinct lists as they are acknowledged from each engine. Duplicate items could perform.

Statement of the Problem:

The present study is on “**Effective use of Internet and Web Technology in Academic College Libraries in Mangalwedha city.** Further researcher is studying whether the users use impact of Internet and Web technology are up-dating their knowledge and get the information of current awareness as per their requirement and as per the needed time.

Scope and Limitations:

This study is confined to the Effective use of Internet and web technology of students in Art, commerce and Science Senior colleges in Mangalwedha city. such as 1) Shri Sant Damaji Mahavidyalya, Mangalwedha 2) Madansinh Mohite-Patil Science Mahavidyalaya, Mangalwedha. So this study is limited to only two colleges, in Mangalwedha city.

Objectives of the Study:

The purpose of this study is to find out the Effective use of Internet and Web technology of Academic library of Art, Commerce & Science students the specific objectives of the Present studies are as follows.

1. To find out what is the perception of the librarian and students facing any problems.
2. To study the frequency of internet and web technology usage for seeking information.
3. To know whether the internet has reduced the number of visitors to the academic college library.
4. To study impact of internet and web technology in libraries of the users.
5. To study effective use of Internet and Web Technology in libraries.

Importance of Study:

Any types of information play a very important role in student life. The Students are trying to get information so they can increase their knowledge. This study effective use of Internet and Web technology in Academic College Libraries in Mangalwedha city. This study only impact of a library for a Internet and Web technology services. An effective use of Internet Web technology for study on Arts,

Commerce and Science Colleges in Mangalwedha city.

Research Methodology:

Researches make a good scientist who helps our society to solve their problems. The present study is undertaken to throw light on “**Effective use of Internet and Web Technology in Academic College Libraries in Mangalwedha city: A Study**”. Research methodology is a way to systematically present our knowledge where as to solve problem. The word self indicates its meaning re-search or searching of new things which is useful to create something new novel. It is must know the entire researcher, what is the accurate methods to do research because research does not allow without systemizes and techniques. There are many methods of data collection and survey & descriptive research.

Descriptive Method:

Descriptive method is the simplest and is applicable to a number of social problems especially in under developed countries. It is essentially a fact finding research related to present study and current situation.

Questionnaire Tool:

The data required for the survey is collected through questionnaire technique. In this method questionnaire is sent to respondent who are expected to read and write down the reply in the space meant for purpose in the questionnaire itself. On the basis of these guidelines a detailed questionnaire was prepared considering the present study. The questionnaires and as a response the questionnaires will be received with filled information. The researcher will be considering these questionnaires for the data analysis.

In this research study the researcher has used the self prepared

questionnaire and distributed within the library users of Mangalwedha city colleges and collected the data. Further, the researcher will made the findings, suggestions and conclusions on the basis of the analysis of the all gathered questionnaire in the form of percentage, tables and diagrams. The study **Effective use of Internet and Web Technology in Academic College Libraries in Mangalwedha city: A Study** for the

present study. The researcher has used the random sampling method for research.

Sample Design:

There are only two colleges for present study.

Name of colleges in Mangalwedha city:-

1. SDM: Shri Sant Damaji Mahavidyalaya, Mangalwedha
2. MMP: Madansinh Mohite-Patil Science Mahavidyalaya, Mangalwedha

Table No: - 1: Distribution of Response

Sr. No	Type of Users	Questionnaire Distributed	Total of Numbers		Percentage	
			Respondent	Non-Respondent	%	%
1	Male	100	85	15	85	15
2	Female	170	165	05	97.6	2.94
	Total	270	250	20	100	

From the above Table No: 1 show that, number of Male & Female respondent. There are 270 questionnaire distributed between 270 respondent. That 100 Male & 170 Female were included, but only 85 Male & 165 Female responded to this questionnaire and 15 Male & 05 Female ignored to this questionnaire. It means that 85% Male & 97.5% Female are good respondent so 15% Male & 2.94% Female are not good respondent.

Graph No: - 1: Type of Documents

Table No: - 2: Type of book respondent read

Type of Document	Respondent	Percentage (%)
Reference books	125	50
Text books	100	40
Periodicals	25	10
Total	250	100

The above table No-2 and Graph No-1 shows that the type of respondent read. The 125 students are responded as Reference books and their percentage is 50%. The 100 Students are responded as text books and their percentage is 40%. The 25 students read periodicals and their percentage is 10%.

Table No:-3: Frequency of using library

Frequency	No. of students	Percentage(%)
2-3 times daily	25	10
Daily	75	30
Occasionally	25	10
When necessary	125	50
Total	250	100

Graph No: 2 Frequency of using library

The above table No-3 and Graph No-2 shows that the type of Frequency of using Library. The 125 students are responded as when necessary and their percentage is 50%. The 75 Students are responded as daily and their percentage is 30%. The 25 students are using 2-3 times daily and their percentage is 10%. The 25 students are using occasionally and their percentage 10%.

Table No:4 Accessing Internet and Web Technology in libraries

Type of Answer	Respondent	Percentage (%)
Yes	225	90
No	25	10
Total	250	100

Graph No:3 Accessing Internet and Web Technology in libraries

The Table No-4 and Graph No-3 indicates that the responded are Access internet and web technology in libraries. The 225 Students are responded access internet and web technology in libraries and their percentage is 90%. The 25 students do not access internet and web technology and their percentage is 10%.

Table No: - 5. Effective Use Internet and Web technology

Internet Access	Respondent	Percentage (%)
Regularly	100	40
Sometime	125	50
Rarely	25	10
Total	250	100

Graph No-4 Effective Use Internet and Web technology**Effective use internet and web technology**

The above table No- 5 and Graph No-4 shows that Using effective use of internet and web technology. The 100 student's uses regularly use internet and web technology and their percentage is 40%. The 125 Students uses sometime use internet and their percentage is 50% and only 25 Students uses rarely access internet and their percentage is 10%. Mostly Students are using internet and web technology sometime.

Table No: - 6 Respondent Effective use to satisfy information through Internet and Web technology

Type of Answer	Respondent	Percentage (%)
Yes	200	80
No	50	20
Total	250	100

Graph No: 5 Effective uses to satisfy information through Internet and Web technology

The Table No-6 and Graph No-5 indicate that the responded are satisfied through internet and web technology in libraries. The 200 Students are responded satisfied internet and web technology in libraries and their percentage is 80%. The 50 students not satisfied internet and web technology and their percentage is 20%.

Findings:

- 1) The 125 students are responded as when necessary and their percentage is 50%. The 75

Students are responded as daily and their percentage is 30%. The 25 students are using 2-3 times daily and their percentage is 10%. The 25 students are using occasionally and their percentage 10%.

- 2) The 225 Students are responded access internet and web technology in libraries and their percentage is 90%. The 25 students do not access internet and web technology and their percentage is 10%.
- 3) The 100 student's uses regularly use internet and web technology and their percentage is 40%. The 125 Students uses sometime use internet and their percentage is 50% and only 25 Students uses rarely access internet and their percentage is 10%. Mostly Students are using internet and web technology sometime.
- 4) The 200 Students are responded satisfied internet and web technology in libraries and their percentage is 80%. The 50 students not satisfied internet and web technology and their percentage is 20%.

Suggestions:

- 1) The internet and web technology can effective use increased by academic college libraries in Mangalwedha city.
- 2) Library orientation programs should be carried out for users at least once in a year to
- 3) Understand the entire internet and web technology available in the academic college libraries.
- 4) Every academic college library should provide Technological Infrastructure for Accessing E-Resources; it should be contain

college Network, Campus Wi-Fi and Computer Labs in Libraries.

- 5) Every academic college library should provide many web services through internet web technology.
- 6) To increase satisfy level on students and users in academic college libraries through internet and web technology.

Conclusion:

The Internet and web technology has what it takes to transforms education at all levels. What is needed is the provision of right infrastructure to serve as the vehicle for the Internet to the colleges. Internet facilities on the many college campuses are characterized by poor or slow internet speed. This situation has the potency to limit effective use of the Internet technology for the knowledge access through college libraries. Applications of web technologies in academic college library have changed with the advancement of information technology through internet. Every academic college library working on library portal is called as the “Mirror of the Library”. It is the duty of library and information professionals to remain updated with the latest developments to render web-based services to their users and pay personal attention during the service tenure. Documentation centre provide special services to special users. Library and information professionals wish to provide information to their users. They have curiosity to interact with the members and utmost desire to provide required information at the least possible time. Web services can empower libraries, simpler system customization and integration. These advantages are

dependent on web services being standardized. Not only Library and information professionals but user should also be provided training about the applications of web based library services from time to time accessing in academic college libraries.

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